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2 **Sliceable BVT evolution towards programmable** 3 **multi-Tb/s networking**

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9 **Abstract:** The sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT) has become a key element to
10 address the challenging and evolution of optical networks, in order to support the ever increasing
11 traffic volume, speed and dynamicity, driven by novel and broadband services and applications.
12 Multiple designs and configurations are possible and are evolving towards supporting multi-Tb/s
13 networking, also thanks to the adoption of advanced and more mature photonic technologies. In this
14 work, we review and analyze alternative S-BVT design architecture options able to target different
15 network segments and applications. We specifically focus on S-BVTs based on multicarrier
16 modulation (MCM), which provide a wide range of granularity and more flexible spectral
17 manipulation. A detailed description of the main elements composing an S-BVT and their
18 characteristics is provided in order to give design guidelines. The performance in a real testbed
19 network is also reported, comparing a set of S-BVT configurations adopting different technologies.
20 Finally, an extensive discussion of the described architectures, functionalities and results, including
21 programmability aspects, is provided in view of an S-BVT evolution towards future optical network
22 requirements and needs.

23 **Keywords:** sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT); orthogonal frequency division
24 multiplexing (OFDM); discrete multitone (DMT); direct detection; coherent detection; vertical cavity
25 surface emitting laser (VCSEL)

26

27 **1. Introduction**

28 In recent years, we are witnessing a fast growing of the speed and volume of traffic driven by
29 novel and broadband (5G) services. In order to accommodate these changes, optical networks are
30 evolving towards a more dynamic, flexible, programmable and open paradigm, while novel and
31 suitable technologies are explored and exploited, improving their readiness level, towards
32 supporting this new paradigm and providing solutions to the related challenges [1-5]. In this context,
33 the bandwidth variable transceiver (BVT), with its advanced functionalities and the ability of being
34 sliceable (S-BVT), has assumed an especially relevant role in the research community during the last
35 years, following the roadmap of optical networks [5-9]. A BVT is a transceiver able to dynamically
36 vary the optical bandwidth and/or bitrate and adapt to the condition of the established path by
37 selecting specific parameters such as the modulation format, the operating wavelength, the target
38 rate/performance or the forward error correction (FEC) coding. The parameter set configuration is
39 delegated to software control according to the traffic demand and targeted reach. A BVT can address
40 a single traffic demand on a single portion of the optical spectrum over a specific network path
41 between the source node and the destination node (also referred to as media-channel). The S-BVT is
42 an evolution of BVT enabling multiple independent flows to be routed into different media-channels
43 towards the same or multiple destination nodes (inverse multiplexing) [6]. Accordingly, the S-BVT
44 supports flexible and programmable multi-flow, multi-rate, multi-format and multi-reach
45 transmission [7]. It can be seen as a set of virtual transceivers, which are suitably enabled to generate

46 super-channels, simultaneously serving multiple independent traffic demands [6-7]. In addition to
47 this super-wavelength granularity (in the optical domain) associated to the multiple optical carriers
48 (i.e. operating wavelength of each BVT), also it is possible to enable spectral manipulation at sub-
49 wavelength granularity (at electrical/digital level) in every single BVT, resulting in a much wider
50 range of granularities. This is achieved adopting multicarrier modulation (MCM), namely, discrete
51 multitone (DMT) or orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM). This approach enables to
52 fully exploit the spectral dimension, especially in flexi-grid networks with granularity of 6.25 GHz
53 and 12.5 GHz, or even finer [10]. Furthermore, MCM technologies enable self-performance
54 monitoring thanks to the overhead of information (e.g. training symbols, TS) allocated for channel
55 estimation and equalization [11].

56 In addition to spectrum, also other dimensions can be exploited, such as polarization and space
57 in order to further increase system/network capacity. Polarization division multiplexing (PDM)
58 allows doubling the spectral efficiency (SE), as well as introducing an additional dimension that can
59 be also used for routing additional traffic in dense fiber links [12]. Space division multiplexing (SDM)
60 allows scaling the capacity of a factor depending on the number of fibers/cores and/or modes used in
61 case of adopting fiber bundles or multicore fibers (MCF) and/or multimode (few-mode) fibers [13].
62 Multi-dimensionality allows enhancing the S-BVT performance and improving flexibility as well as
63 the supported capacity towards Tb/s networking not only for long-haul, but also for the metro and
64 access segment [14-16]. In fact, the evolutionary path of optical networks, in view of supporting novel
65 and bandwidth-hungry applications, affects all segments. Especially for metropolitan area networks
66 (MANs), as one of the most challenging among the segments, it is becoming particularly relevant and
67 most prominent, as forecasted in [17]. Specific tailored solutions must be envisioned to address the
68 high demand of dynamicity and capacity, while coping with the stringent cost and energy
69 requirements. Accordingly, the role of mature and novel photonic technologies as well as dense
70 photonic integration, able to reduce the cost, power consumption and footprint is particularly
71 important for an actual and optimal design of the transceiver architecture [18-19].

72 The purpose of this work is to review and analyze alternative S-BVT design architecture options
73 targeting different network segments and applications, also including programmability aspects. We
74 specifically focus on S-BVT architectures based on MCM, which provide a wide range granularity. In
75 Section 2, we describe the S-BVT architecture, detailing its main elements, and provide design
76 guidelines. The S-BVT performance details and latest results achieved in a real testbed network are
77 reported in Section 3. Furthermore, S-BVT programmability is also discussed in this Section, towards
78 the integration of the proposed data plane solutions with a control plane, relying on, for example, a
79 centralized software defined networking (SDN) controller. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions,
80 discussing the described architectures, functionalities and results, with a look towards future optical
81 network requirements and needs, providing our vision of S-BVT evolution and what's next.

82 2. S-BVT architecture: design and options

83 An S-BVT general architecture is depicted in Figure 1. It is worth noting the modular scheme,
84 based on multiple BVT modules, which ease the grow/pay-as-needed approach, facilitating optical
85 network disaggregation and fostering interoperability [9, 19]. When photonic integration is
86 considered, the fundamental/basic module can include multiple BVT front-end modules, which can
87 be activated in a license-based fashion.

88 In Figure 1, we identify multiple block/elements per each BVT at the transmitter (BVTx) and
89 receiver (BVRx), implemented with different technologies and enabling different functionalities:

- 90 • Digital signal processing (DSP)
- 91 • Digital-to-analogue converter (DAC) and analogue-to-digital converter (ADC)
- 92 • Optoelectronic front-end
- 93 • Multi-flow (MF) aggregator and distributor.

94
95 **Figure 1.** Schematic of a programmable (SDN-enabled) S-BVT. Digital and analogue domains are
96 indicated.

97 At each BVT module, the DSP supports MCM, either DMT or OFDM. DMT represents a more
98 cost-effective solution based on real-valued signal flows. It is typically used for intensity modulation
99 in the optical domain, to be easily recovered with DD. However, this scheme is severely affected by
100 the chromatic dispersion (CD), resulting a solution suitable for short distances. OFDM enables the
101 generation of complex-valued signals and can be combined also with linear field (amplitude) and
102 single-sideband (SSB) modulation, to be recovered either with direct detection (DD) or coherent
103 receiver (CO-Rx). The mapper enables uniform loading (UL) of the digital/electrical DMT/OFDM
104 subcarriers. There is a trade-off between spectral efficiency (SE) and transmission reach. Since for
105 short-reach connections, modulation formats with higher SE can be adopted, while in case of long-
106 haul links more robust formats (with less SE) should be used. In case of adaptive DSP, a mapper
107 supporting multiple formats is included. This allows adopting the most suitable modulation format
108 per subcarrier in order to maximize the BVT performance, according to the channel state information
109 (CSI), as shown in the inset of Figure 1. The sub-wavelength granularity is defined as the ratio
110 between the slice/flow bandwidth (B) and the number of electrical/digital DMT/OFDM subcarriers
111 (N_{sc}). For example, considering a B=20 GHz and 512=N_{sc}, the subcarrier spacing and thus the
112 minimum sub-wavelength granularity is 39 MHz.

113 The DAC converts the digital signal into the analogue domain; the sample rate can vary
114 according to the adopted device, trading (similarly to ADC) high performance in terms of speed and
115 bandwidth with cost and complexity [20]. After the DAC, the flow/slice is converted to the optical
116 domain by means of an optoelectronic front-end, which can be based on direct laser modulation
117 (DML) or external modulation. The flows are combined by the MF aggregator and transmitted over
118 the network. At the receiver side, the MF after being distributed is received at the specific BVRx front-
119 end, which can be based either on DD or CO-Rx. The ADC converts the flow to the digital domain to
120 be post-processed at the BVRx DSP.

121 The S-BVT can be programmable: an SDN controller by means of an S-BVT agent (or more
122 specifically S-BVTx and S-BVRx agents) configures the programmable/variable parameters in both
123 the digital and analogue domains. So that different slices/flows can be suitably enabled/disabled, as
124 well as the occupied frequency slots (i.e. the bandwidth occupancy) and optical carrier (operating
125 wavelength), the target rate or FEC selected, etc. [7, 9, 19].

126 In the following subsections, we provide further details on specific S-BVT elements and
127 functionalities.

129 2.1. DSP

130 In order to generate a real-valued signal for intensity modulation, after serial to parallel (S/P)
 131 conversion of the input data and suitable mapping, either the real-valued fast Fourier transform (FFT)
 132 or the fast Hartley transform (FHT) can be applied, as shown in Figure 2. The latter processing
 133 enabling the use of one-dimensional constellations, specifically M -ary pulse-amplitude modulation
 134 (M -PAM) format, and simplified channel estimation to obtain the same spectral efficiency and
 135 performance as the FFT processing with M^2 -ary quadrature amplitude modulation (M^2 -QAM) format
 136 [21]. Thanks to the FHT inherent symmetry and self-inverse property, a low-complexity fast
 137 processor can be applied, providing an attractive alternative for an actual implementation of MCM-
 138 based transceivers. Finally, cyclic prefix (CP) is appended before parallel to serial (P/S) conversion.
 139

140 **Figure 2.** BVTx DSP implementing DMT based on (a) FFT; (b) FHT.

141 The individual subcarrier can be adaptively modulated by applying a bit loading (BL) algorithm,
 142 using adaptive modulation formats (e.g. binary phase shift keying, BPSK, and L -QAM, with $L=2^n$ and
 143 $2 \leq n \leq 8$) at the DSP mapper, for achieving multiple rate/reach. For subcarrier with low signal-to-noise
 144 ratio (SNR), more robust and less efficient modulation format (less number of loaded bits) are used,
 145 and vice versa in case of high SNR. Similarly, also the power value of each subcarrier can be suitably
 146 assigned by applying power loading (PL).

147 Optimal or suboptimal algorithms (e.g. Levin-Campello or Chow-Cioffi- Bingham [22]) can be
 148 adopted for the BL/PL assignment to the individual subcarriers. The algorithms can be rate adaptive
 149 (RA) and margin adaptive (MA). The former maximizes the data rate for a fixed S-BVT performance,
 150 while the latter maximizes the S-BVT performance at a given data rate. Loading strategies can be
 151 similarly applied to FFT-based or FHT-based S-BVT DSP, in case of FHT the mirror symmetric
 152 subcarrier property of this alternative transform should be considered [23]. In case of adaptive DSP,
 153 by selecting the *estimation mode*, UL (e.g. using 4-QAM format) is applied to retrieve the CSI by means
 154 of the SNR profile (see top left inset of Figure 1). With this information, the *data flow mode* can be
 155 activated for an optimal BL/PL assignment, according to the target rate/performance over the
 156 established connection.

157 For a successful performance, the bit error rate (BER) threshold (e.g. 10^{-3} , $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$, or $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$) is set
 158 considering the applied FEC coding. To limit the overhead to 7%, hard decision (HD) FEC is adopted;
 159 increasing the FEC overhead up to 20%, applying a soft decision (SD) FEC, higher bit rate can be
 160 transmitted or either longer reach can be covered.

161 In order to mitigate the high peak to average power ratio (PAPR) of the OFDM signal, a clipping
 162 DSP module can be applied. To mitigate the signal distortion due to the clipping noise, an optimal
 163 clipping level is selected according to the modulation formats assigned by the mapper. Distortion-
 164 less PAPR reduction techniques can also be eventually implemented at the BVTx DSP [24].

165 At the DSP, also digital up- and down-conversion at an intermediate radio frequency can be
 166 applied according to the selected modulation scheme, this element is particularly relevant in case of
 167 adopting multi-band OFDM [8].

168 In case of adopting CO-Rx, the DSP at the receiver side requires additional modules (e.g. carrier
 169 recovery) [8].
 170

171 2.2. S-BVT Front-end Options

172 Alternative S-BVT optoelectronic front-end module options can be adopted, according to the
 173 specific target network segment and application, as shown in Figure 3.

174 Specifically, at the S-BVTx, external (intensity or amplitude) modulation or a directly modulated
 175 laser (DML) can be used. In case of external modulation, a Mach Zehnder modulator (MZM) driven
 176 by a tunable laser source (TLS) are used for flexibly adapt the MZM bias point and the operating
 177 wavelength, respectively. For intensity modulation (IM), the MZM is biased at the quadrature point;
 178 amplitude modulation (AM) is obtained biasing the MZM near to the null point. The S-BVT can be
 179 also designed to have a single multi-wavelength source to drive a set of MZMs, each one belonging
 180 to a different BVT module. This solution is more compact and cost-effective than using an array of
 181 TLS; however, it has limited tune-ability [25].

182 **Figure 3.** Front-end module options for (a) BVTx: DML and external modulator with TLS, (b) BVRx:
 183 DD and CO-Rx.

184 Alternatively, intensity modulation can be obtained with DML, which allows further reducing
 185 the S-BVTx module cost. Particularly, the use of vertical cavity surface emitting laser (VCSEL)
 186 technology can be considered to dramatically reduce the cost, power consumption and footprint [5].
 187 Different VCSEL options can be envisioned to target specific applications, including widely tunable
 188 VCSELs based on micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS), or short-cavity (SC) VCSELs at long
 189 wavelengths characterized by large bandwidth (>18GHz) [26-28].

190 At the S-BVRx, either cost-effective DD, with a simple PIN photodetector (PD) followed by a
 191 transimpedance amplifier (TIA), or a more complex CO-Rx (see Figure 3b) can be adopted, including
 192 a local laser (local oscillator LO) and a suitable optical hybrid.

193 2.3. MF Aggregator/distributor

194 The aggregator/distributor can be a programmable and bandwidth-variable (BV) wavelength
 195 selective switch (WSS), implemented in liquid crystal on silicon (LCoS) technology. This S-BVT
 196 element can be also realized using photonic integrated circuit (PIC) technology to be a simple and
 197 cost-effective passive element. This option limits the flexibility and programmability of the
 198 transceiver architecture, even though with the advent of programmable photonics, it is possible to
 199 envision future attractive solutions [29]. A hybrid and electro-optical MCM scheme exploiting both
 200 super- and sub-wavelength granularity is proposed and assessed in [30], where the multiple flows
 201 are packed into super-channels by optically implementing the discrete wavelet packet transform
 202 (DWPT) and its inverse. This allows increasing the S-BVT spectral efficiency and can be either
 203 implemented by suitably programming an LCoS-based BV-WSS or using Mach-Zehnder
 204 interferometers integrated employing silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology.

205 2.4. Functionalities

206 Multiple advanced features and functionalities are enabled by adopting a MCM-based S-BVT,
 207 eased by its integration in an SDN control plane. Particularly, MCM and adaptive DSP enable
 208 rate/distance adaptability for an optimal spectrum usage. Furthermore, unique granularity and grid
 209 adaptation is obtained thanks to the hybrid tune-ability of optical carrier (for example adopting a
 210 TLS) and adaptive subcarrier loading/allocation. Slice-ability, inverse multiplexing and
 211 defragmentation are also supported, together with an SDN-enabled MF generation and

212 routing/switching of the multiple slices on the network. Furthermore, SDN-enabled S-BVT also
 213 facilitate a soft migration of fixed grid networks towards a flexi-grid paradigm. In [7], these
 214 functionalities are described in details and their assessment provided for an S-BVT with multiple
 215 modules and technologies, supporting a total capacity above 200 Gb/s.

216 3. Performance and Programmability

217 Taking into account the different elements and options described in Section 2, the suitable S-BVT
 218 design depends on the targeted network segment and application. The fundamental S-BVT elements
 219 can be selected according to their cost/complexity and expected performance, identifying different
 220 flexibility level and requirements as summarized in Table 1. In [7] and [19], more exhaustive
 221 description and discussion of the S-BVT elements and characteristics reported in Table 1 are
 222 provided.

223 For example, transceivers adopting CO-Rx provide high flexibility and ultimate performance
 224 (high capacity for an extended achievable reach), but are more complex and costly than the options
 225 based on DD. Similarly, high-speed and large bandwidth DAC/ADC facilitates the improvement of
 226 S-BVT capacity and performance. Thus, for cost-sensitive applications, the S-BVT design should take
 227 into account these aspects and the trade-offs related with cost, achievable performance and flexibility.

228 **Table 1.** S-BVT elements and characteristics [7, 19]; SE= spectral efficiency; L=low; M=medium;
 229 H=high.

S-BVT element	Type	Bandwidth (B)	Cost/complexity	Performance	Flexibility
DSP-MCM	DMT	$N_{sc} \times B_{sc}$	L	L/M	H
	OFDM ¹	$B_{DSB}/2$ (2xSE)	M	H	H
DSP-algorithm	Adaptive	H SE	H	H	H
	Uniform	L SE	L	L	L
DAC/ADC	H speed	Large	H	H	M/H
	L speed	Narrow	M	L	L
Tx Front-End	DML	Device B	L	M/L	L ³
	Ext. Mod	Device B	M/H ²	H	H ²
Rx Front-End	DD	PD B	L	M/L	L
	CO-Rx	PD B	H	H	H ⁴

230 ¹ SSB-OFDM or with CO-Rx; ³ generally low but depending on tune-ability of DML (e.g. tunable VCSEL);

231 ² assuming to adopt TLS; ⁴ assuming TLO; ⁵ limited BV depending on complexity.

232 According to the different options, alternative S-BVT configurations are possible. Either DMT or
 233 OFDM (with or without SSB), implemented with DML (IM) or external modulation (IM or AM) can
 234 be combined with DD or CO-Rx. We can identify three main configurations: i) DMT with DD, ii) SSB-
 235 OFDM with DD and iii) OFDM with CO-Rx. The first option is the simplest with the lowest
 236 cost/complexity at the expenses of the performance and SE. In fact, the optical B occupation is double
 237 compared to the other configurations and it is the option more affected by the CD at the increasing
 238 of the reach. The achievable reach can be extended adopting the second option, since SSB-OFDM is
 239 more robust against CD. The ultimate performance can be achieved by adopting CO-Rx (with a
 240 tunable LO, TLO, for improved flexibility and adaptability) at the expenses of higher cost and
 241 complexity at the S-BVRx, with respect to the other options. Also, hybrid configurations can be
 242 envisioned combining different module options to match the specific S-BVT element properties and
 243 expected performance with the targeted application or use case. For example, DMT or SSB-OFDM
 244 can be also combined with CO-Rx, for an S-BVT design with simpler and cost-effective S-BVTx able
 245 to cope with longer path and/or more degraded channel.

246 Table 2 shows different S-BVT configurations and the latest experimental results achieved in a
 247 real testbed network, namely the ADRENALINE testbed [31]. This is to provide a performance
 248 comparison of the alternative proposed S-BVT schemes on a same experimental platform. It can be

249 observed that an S-BVT based on DMT with DD supports high-capacity over short path.
 250 Nevertheless, by adopting suitable dispersion compensator, the achievable reach can be extended
 251 even for high-capacity DMT systems, as demonstrated for a programmable 400 Gb/s DMT transceiver
 252 in the same testbed [32].

253 SSB-OFDM is more robust against CD over multi-hop paths and allows obtaining better
 254 performance also with S-BVRx module based on DM-VCSEL (the table reports results for widely
 255 tunable MEMS-VCSELs) [33]. Finally, as shown in [30], CO-Rx allows achieving high robustness
 256 against accumulated dispersion.

257 **Table 2.** Experimental results in ADRENALINE testbed for different S-BVT configurations.

MCM	S-BVTx Front-end	S-BVRx Front-end	Opt. B ¹	Capacity	Path	hop #	FEC limit	Ref
DMT	Ext. Mod.	DD	50 GHz	110 Gb/s	35 km	1	3·10 ⁻³	[7]
DMT	DM-VCSEL (MEMS)	DD	25 GHz	21 Gb/s 12 Gb/s	35 km 185 km	1 2	4.62·10 ⁻³	[32]
SSB-OFDM	MZM&TLS (IM)	DD	25 GHz	50 Gb/s 35 Gb/s	35 km ² 120 km ³	1 3	4.62·10 ⁻³	[9]
SSB-OFDM	DM-VCSEL (MEMS)	DD	12.5 GHz	28 Gb/s 20 Gb/s	35 km 185 km	1 2	4.62·10 ⁻³	[32]
OFDM	MZM&TLS (AM)	CO-Rx	12.5 GHz	27 Gb/s 12 Gb/s ⁴	25 km 185 km	- 2	4.62·10 ⁻³ 1·10 ⁻³	[30] [8]

258 ¹optical bandwidth occupation in terms of flexi-grid slots of 12.5 GHz; ² with 50-GHz WSS; ³ with 10 cascading
 259 nodes including 100-GHz AWGs and 50-GHz WSS; ⁴ 10 Gb/s net target bitrate (UL) connection.

260 As described in Figure 4, the ADRENALINE testbed network consists of four nodes: two optical
 261 cross-connects (OXC) and two reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs); two of
 262 them (OXC-2 and ROADM-1) are equipped with programmable BV-WSS modules, enabling flexi-
 263 grid connections. The fixed-grid connections are based on 100-GHz and 50-GHz arrayed waveguide
 264 gratings (AWGs). The mesh network has five links ranging from 35 km to 150 km, for a total of 600
 265 km of standard single mode fibers (G.652 and G.655). The network links are amplified by erbium-
 266 doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs).

267 As shown in Table 2, the effect of traversing multiple nodes and, thus, multiple filtering stages,
 268 degrades the performance (filter narrowing effect) and should be taken into account for an optimal
 269 design [9, 34-35]. This effect is particularly detrimental when the filter bandwidth is narrow (<25
 270 GHz) and therefore most prominent in flexi-grid networks.

271 **Figure 4.** ADRENALINE testbed network with paths considered in Table 2 (left) and picture
 272 indicating the testbed network elements (right).
 273

274 In order to scale with the capacity, multiple modules can be integrated in the S-BVT and multiple
 275 dimensions can be exploited, including the full available spectrum, the polarization and the space.
 276 Particularly, a cost-effective S-BVT adopting DD with PDM capability has been proposed and
 277 demonstrated in [36], where the polarization mode dispersion (PMD) effect is also analyzed for the
 278 proposed transceiver scheme.

279 The adoption of MB-OFDM lowers the number of required optoelectronic blocks at the S-BVT
280 to serve multiple endpoints of an optical network. For example, to target a total capacity of 1 Tb/s,
281 considering 10 Gb/s connections and 5 bands per each flow, at most 20 BVT modules would be
282 required, serving up to 100 endpoints. In [8] it has been demonstrated from a techno-economic point
283 of view, that an S-BVT using MB-OFDM based on external modulation (MZM and TLS) and DD is a
284 viable solution (compared to coherent flexi-grid transponders envisioned for core networks) for
285 metro network applications, covering regional paths up to hundreds of kilometers.

286 Alternatively, in order to further reduce the S-BVTx cost, power consumption and footprint, the
287 use of multiple modules adopting VCSEL technology (in particular SC-VCSEL with large bandwidth)
288 combined with dense photonic integration is an attractive solution. It has been recently proposed and
289 is currently explored to support multi-Tb/s capacity/connections [16, 19, 28]. A fundamental module
290 with 40 VCSELs integrated on a SOI-chip is capable to support up to 2 Tb/s. Following a modular
291 approach, the C-band can be efficiently exploited with a full-featured S-BVT equipped with multiple
292 modules, populating the spectrum with 25GHz-spaced flows supporting up to 50 Gb/s each, for a
293 total capacity of 8 Tb/s, which can be doubled with PDM. In order to extend the achievable reach, for
294 example to target very large MAN, CO-Rx can be envisioned with a simplified DSP [19, 28]. So far,
295 promising results have been obtained in view of validating this S-BVT architecture towards multi-
296 Tb/s networking [16]. In fact, above 100 Tb/s are achieved with 7 fibers in a bundle or 7 cores of a
297 MCF.

298 299 3.1. Programmability

300 The remote configuration of the S-BVT is performed by means of specific agents (see Fig. 1),
301 which are software component that enables to map high-level operation requests from the SDN
302 controller into hardware-dependent operations. The SDN controller configures the S-BVT over an
303 established network connection, according to the received request and based on the elements and
304 features described in Section 2.

305 Depending on the S-BVT design and specific configuration, multiple parameters can be selected.
306 Examples of S-BVT parameters to be set are the enabled flow (S-BVT module and/or module element),
307 the operating wavelength, the DSP algorithm (RA/MA), the target rate or performance, FEC, etc. [7].

308 Indeed, the specificities of the adopted configuration and/or technologies (e.g. the use of VCSEL
309 or TLS with external modulation, DD or CO-Rx) as well as the limited tune-ability and/or flexibility
310 of the considered solution, should be taken into account for the S-BVT modeling and
311 programmability handled by the SDN controller [19]. Yet another next generation (YANG) models
312 are used to adopt a common language to describe the network elements to be controlled and
313 managed, easing a migration towards disaggregated optical networks and a multi-vendor scenario
314 [3, 9]. Example of YANG models including proof of concept validations of S-BVT programmability
315 considering different S-BVT configurations, based on alternative technologies, can be found in [19,
316 30, 37].

317 4. Conclusions and future perspective

318 In this work, we have reviewed S-BVT architectures based on MCM. We propose to adopt a
319 modular design to provide a more flexible and scalable solution in view of the evolutionary path of
320 optical networks towards a more dynamic, disaggregated and ultra-high capacity networking.
321 Different module options are presented, emphasizing pros and cons. For a suitable design, the
322 specific network segment or targeted application should be taken into account in order to select the
323 best option of each element and the related trade-offs, considering costs and performance.

324 The efficient exploitation of multiple dimensions with the softwarization and intelligent control
325 of data plane allows an optimal usage of the available resources for the design of high capacity and
326 dynamic as well as highly scalable next generation optical networks.

327 We propose to adopt adaptive DSP, implementing BL and PL to improve the achievable
328 performance and the flexibility, thanks to the wide range tune-ability and spectral manipulation at
329 sub-wavelength level. UL is used to estimate the CSI, which represents a valuable information for

330 performance monitoring and adaptation to the traffic demand and channel state. This allows
331 allocating and managing the network resources while coping with signal degradation, to ensure
332 quality of service.

333 Different S-BVT configurations have been presented and latest experimental results, obtained in
334 a real testbed network, reported, in order to compare the different approaches, with the aim of
335 providing design guidelines and suitably selecting the S-BVT elements. Dense photonic integration
336 and the use of novel, advanced and more mature photonic devices/technologies allow to enable
337 multi-Tb/s networking with reduced cost, power consumption and footprint. Particularly, promising
338 results have been obtained adopting modular S-BVT based on DM SC-VCSEL at long wavelengths.

339 In view of the network evolution, the integration of data and control plane facilitates the
340 implementation of novel advanced functionalities and elements towards the achievement of flexible
341 and highly scalable S-BVT. The S-BVT programmability and modularity foster a migration towards
342 flexi-grid and disaggregated networks. Particularly, this eases a grow-as-needed approach as well as
343 a smooth migration from chassis-based (proprietary) network elements to white boxes, enabling
344 interoperability.

345 With a future perspective, we believe that next generation S-BVT will be based on advanced
346 programmable modular photonic transceivers and that this S-BVT evolution paves the way for a
347 convergence of optical, inter- and intra-data center networks.

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